

Introduction to the multi-actor approach

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

An introduction video presentation (25 min.) from a European Commission official on what the multi-actor approach (MAA) is in the Horizon Europe framework and the crucial elements to integrate while building or joining a multi-actor proposal.

Benefits

This video provides key insights on: the definition of the MAA, expectations & key requirements related to the MAA in Horizon Europe - Cluster 6 proposals. It helps in getting better acquainted with central terms and concepts often used in multi-actor project proposal processes.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Active participation of, and focus on end-users

Work with a diversity of backgrounds

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Link to the video presentation](#)

**right click to open*

Practical recommendations

This video explains the basics of the MAA. It is a useful resource to get acquainted with some concepts and terms often used in the context of multi-actor project proposals such as:

- AKIS;
- the EU policy context: European Green Deal, CAP (Common Agricultural Policy), Farm to Fork Strategy, Horizon Europe, etc.;
- Co-creation;
- EIP-AGRI Operational Groups;
- Relevant stakeholder groups.

In the second half of the video, it goes deeper into requirements, eligibility criteria and expectations with regards to MA project proposals.